

Control of Magnetism of Co-Phthalocyanine by ferromagnetic substrate

By *E. Annese*^{1,*}, *J. Fujii*¹, *I. Vobornik*¹, *G. Panaccione*¹ and *G. Rossi*^{1,2}

[*] Dr. E. Annese
TASC Laboratory, IOM-CNR,
SS 14, km 163.5, I-34149 Trieste, Italy
E-mail: annese@tasc.infm.it

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One of the basic ideas in spintronics is to achieve the control of spin alignment by electrical manipulation.^[1] Nowadays, organic spin valves operating at low temperature show magneto-resistance response with an applied bias of few millivolts.^[2] The role of the magnetic coupling between organic films and magnetic substrate can be important in determining the hybrid device performances and their operating conditions. The occurrence of molecular magnetism at room temperature and the understanding of its mechanism represent one of the challenging issues. Molecular magnets represent a promising option in spin manipulation in the contest of minimizing the single magnetic unit.^[3-5] They have the advantage to be more flexible with respect to single adatom^[6] and their weak spin-orbit and hyperfine interactions should favour the spin current over times and distances much longer than metal and semiconductors.^[7,8] Among molecular magnet, metal phthalocyanines (MPc) have already impressed for their application in chemical sensors, optoelectronic devices, in solar cells and in field-effect transistor.^[9] What makes them unique as similar metallo-organic molecules is their potentiality to tune their structural, chemical, magnetic, transport properties by means of different cations within the macrocycle or by moving some atoms from ligands.

Here we address the magnetic coupling of metallo-organic molecules with a ferromagnetic substrate at room temperature and we relate it with the molecules adsorption geometry and electronic structure. We choose as MPc the Co-Phthalocyanine (CoPc) and as a magnetic substrate iron film grown on Cu(111).

Fe magnetization switches from perpendicular (thickness < 5 ML) to parallel to the surface (thickness > 10 ML). This substrate permits to explore the coupling of the magnetic moment of the molecule along to preferential direction, depending on the thickness of the substrate. We observe that CoPc molecules adsorb with their molecular plane parallel to the iron film. Co 3d occupancy and therefore Co electronic structure are strongly affected by iron film. From magnetic point of view a ferromagnetic coupling between Co atom and iron film occurs.

CoPc can be magnetic and its molecular magnetism arises from unpaired spin in 3d orbitals of the host central atom. CoPc has uncompensated magnetic moment of $1.09 \mu_B$ (much smaller than isolated Co^{2+} ion, i.e. $4.8 \mu_B$), but it is paramagnetic. Its magnetic moment fluctuates under thermal activation. Magnetic substrate offers the interesting possibility of controlling CoPc spin. The magnetic coupling occurs when molecules preserve their magnetic moment at interface and spins in individual molecule undergo ordering due to substrate magnetic field. A fundamental understanding of the basic interactions of magnetic molecules with surfaces is essential, because molecules behave differently depending on the environment they are placed in. In this context we investigated the local arrangement and orientation of the molecules was by scanning tunnelling microscopy (STM) and angle dependent X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS).

The three steps of hybrid organic magnetic junction preparation observed by STM are reported in Figure 1: clean Cu(111) surface (a), iron film (b); CoPc monolayer (ML). Figure 1b displays the morphology of 20 ML Fe after thermal treatment: the surface is uniformly covered by 3D Fe clusters of lateral dimension $16 \times 20 \text{ nm}^2$ (in average) corresponding to Fe(110) bcc structure. Molecules adsorb flat with their macrocycle parallel to Fe clusters surface and organize with a molecule-molecule distance of $\sim 1.5\text{-}1.6 \text{ nm}$ (Figure 1c-d). CoPc are identified as a four-lobed pattern (related to the four aromatic rings).

In Figure 1e we report N $1s$ XAS spectrum for 1ML, 6ML CoPc on iron film and 1ML of CoPc on Cu(111) ($\theta = 60^\circ$). The spectra are characterized by sharp features ($1s \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition) below threshold (403.6 eV) and broader features ($1s \rightarrow \sigma^*$ transition) above. The N $1s$ XAS spectrum for multilayer shows peculiar features due to the contribution of two inequivalent N atoms (N_1 and N_2 as defined in Figure 1g). The layer of CoPc in direct contact with iron film, show broadened features in π^* region differently from multilayer. The broadening of spectral features is the consequence of the different environment of N atoms. The adsorption of CoPc on iron increases the number of inequivalent N atoms. This behaviour is peculiar of CoPc/Fe interface, in fact the broadening is not observed for CoPc adsorbed on Cu(111).

In planar π -conjugated systems π^* orbitals are expected to be out of molecular plane, while σ^* are oriented in the molecular plane. Discrimination between the states can therefore be obtained by the search light effect in XAS with linearly polarized light. Figure 1e displays N K edge XAS performed for 1ML CoPc/Fe/Cu(111) at normal (0°) and grazing (60°) incidence, with polarization vector \mathbf{E} parallel and perpendicular to the molecule plane (experimental geometry reported in Figure 1h). The disappearance of the π^* resonances (except for a residual intensity at circa 496.8 eV) when \mathbf{E} is in the molecule plane demonstrates that N atoms lay in a plane parallel to the substrate.

Molecule/substrate interaction is investigated by chemical sensitive probe as X-ray photoemission and absorption spectroscopy. The binding energy position and line shape of core-hole photoemission spectra probe the molecule/substrate interaction. In Figure 2 a-b C $1s$ and N $1s$ core level spectra for CoPc/Cu(111) system is reported for 1ML and multilayer CoPc. The C $1s$ core-level photoemission spectrum of multilayer CoPc/Fe/Cu show the peculiar features relative to two inequivalent C atoms (C_{benz} and C_{pyr}) and satellites originated by shake-up $\pi^* \rightarrow \pi^*$. To describe C $1s$ XPS spectrum we used a fitting function as shown in Figure 2 a. The relevant parameters of the fitting are $C_{\text{benz}}-C_{\text{pyr}}$ peak separation and the relative intensity of these spectral features. Interaction with Fe substrate leads to

binding energy shift of C features of circa 0.2 eV to lower binding energy and a reduction of $C_{\text{benz}}-C_{\text{pyr}}$ energy separation (from 1.38 eV in multilayer to 1.25 eV in ML). Moreover, we observe a reduced ratio for benzene/pyrrole features with respect to the expected 3:1. The change in the relative intensity indicates that benzene carbon atoms are more affected by the interaction with the substrate. We note a further change in C $1s$ line shape: the high binding energy side shows an asymmetric tail similar to that of metallic core-level. This asymmetric tail is peculiar for CoPc adsorbed on Fe, in fact is not observed for example in CoPc adsorbed on Cu(111) (see bottom spectrum in figure 2a).

The two inequivalent N atoms of CoPc have binding energies that are not resolved in photoemission spectra. N $1s$ core level spectrum of CoPc multilayer (Figure 2b: top spectrum) consists of a main feature and a faint high binding energy contribution (~ 401 eV) relative to shake up satellites. Due to the interaction with Fe substrate the N $1s$ feature (Figure 2b: bottom spectrum) undergoes to a shift of 0.3 eV to lower binding energy and line shape modifies with the appearance of a further component at lower binding energy (398.5 eV).

Co L_3 XAS data of 1ML CoPc on Fe reveal a strong modification of Co ion electronic structure due to substrate/molecule interaction. L_3 XAS spectra probe the unoccupied s and d states of molecule at Co site. The $3d$ band of the host central atom, Co, is split because of the electrostatic ligand field. In the case of free-like CoPc molecule Co is divalent and the ligand field has D_{4h} symmetry. Figure 2 c-d reports Co L_3 XAS spectra measured at angles θ ranging from 0° to 60° for multilayer and 1ML CoPc films, respectively. The spectrum relative to multilayer shows several spectral features consistent with Co^{2+} valence state.^[12] Similarly to angle dependent N $1s$ XAS, the search light effect reveals spatial distribution of maximum (minimum) unoccupied orbitals ($3d$ in the case of Co). Since $3d$ orbitals are sensitive to the molecular symmetry, the angular dependence of intensities reflects their spatial distribution as well as orientation of molecules on the substrate. In CoPc multilayer, the intensity of

feature at 772 eV increases with theta, whereas the opposite verifies for the remaining features. The feature at low energy side of Co L_3 XAS spectra corresponds to 3d orbital with an out of molecular plane electronic distribution. Due to the interaction with substrate the feature at 772 eV in the Co L_3 XAS spectrum for 1 ML CoPc is quenched and Co 3d orbitals occupancy is modified.

The change in Co 3d occupancy directly influences Co magnetic moment and therefore the magnetic coupling with the substrate. Calculations predict a reduction of one third of Co magnetic moment upon adsorption at Co(111).^[13]

In the present study, we exploit chemical sensitive X-ray Magnetic Circular Dichroism (XMCD) to investigate the magnetic properties of the molecular film and substrate. XMCD exploits the different response when the alignment between magnetization and photon helicity switches from parallel to antiparallel. XMCD signal is correlated to the spin and orbital moment of the molecular central atom.

[14]

For 20ML Fe/Cu(111) the easy axis of magnetization is pointing parallel to the surface, i.e. parallel to the molecular plane of CoPc. XAS and XMCD spectra at Fe $L_{2,3}$ reported in figure 3a show the typical signal corresponding to alignment of Fe spins along surface vector. Fe XMCD asymmetry defined as $\frac{I^+ - I^-}{I^+ + I^-}$ is 18 %. The field dependent Fe L_3 XMCD intensity are reported at fixed photon energy and

describes the element specific Fe square hysteresis loop at room temperature of coercive field of 50 Oersted.

XAS coefficients for parallel and antiparallel orientation of the magnetization and light polarization at Co $L_{2,3}$ edges are reported in Figure 3 c. These spectra are the results of subtraction of row data and spectra measured on iron film without molecules. The data treatment is necessary due to the magnetic contribution at Co $L_{2,3}$ edges energies coming from iron NEXAFS (an order of magnitude smaller than

dichroism at Fe $L_{2,3}$ edges).^[15] The estimated error related to this data analysis is 50% of the measured Co XMCD signal.

The spectrum with magnetization parallel to photon elicity (I^+) shows higher intensity than I^- at L_3 , the opposite verifies at L_2 edge. The difference spectrum does have the same sign of dichroic signal of the iron film, indicating a ferromagnetic coupling of the molecule with the iron film. Co XMCD asymmetry is 3.6 %. No XMCD was detected at Co $L_{2,3}$ edge for multilayer.

Direct exchange coupling has been reported previously between single CoPc molecule on Co nanoisland, when Co is in direct contact with the substrate^[10] or no coupling because of magnetic moment quenching upon adsorption on iron film^[11]. Both results indicate that the magnetic response of the molecule absorbed on the magnetic substrate depends on the adsorption site, electronic density of state of the molecule.

Unlike single atom adsorption on crystal ferromagnet, magnetic molecules have the advantage of a broad flexibility and the variety of atoms within them introduces the occurrence of different mechanism at the origin of the coupling with the substrate. For instance, a possible involvement of N atoms in the magnetic coupling is predicted theoretically. However, N magnetic moment is one tenth of that of Co and efficiency of XMCD at K edge is one tenth of that at L edge, making XMCD measurements at N edge challenging. We do not observe XMCD signal at N K edge within our sensitivity and we exclude in this case the role of N atoms in the coupling between molecule and substrate.

In conclusion, this work demonstrates how the choice of molecules and ferromagnetic substrate plays a critical role in the spin injection efficiency at organic/ferromagnet hybrid interface, a first constituent of organic spintronics device. Experimental results evidence a parallel magnetic coupling between molecule (CoPc) and magnetic substrate (iron film) at interface as well as a strong electrostatic interaction at room temperature. The paramagnetic CoPc molecule aligns its residual magnetic moment

along the magnetization of iron film. The possible contribution of N atoms in the magnetic coupling is not detectable within our sensitivity.

Experimental

Sample preparation and characterizations are performed at APE beamline of IOM-CNR at the ELETTRA Synchrotron Radiation Facility (Trieste). The photon beam provided by xx undulator can both linearly and circular polarized^[16]. XAS measurements were obtained by measuring the sample drain current with an energy resolution of 150 meV. XMCD spectra were recorded with a fixed helicity of the light and opposite magnetization direction. X-ray photoemission (XPS) spectra data have been acquired by a seven channel Omicron EA-125 analyzer at normal emission using linearly polarized X-rays with photon energies of 480 eV. The overall energy resolution was about 200 meV. STM images were acquired with a home-made STM, operating in UHV with atomic resolution. All measurements are recorded at RT. The preparation and characterization chambers are connected in UHV. The Cu(111) substrate is prepared *in situ* by several cycles of Ar⁺ sputtering and annealing. Iron is deposited on the substrate by electron beam evaporator in a base pressure of 10⁻¹⁰ mbar. CoPc is evaporated in situ by molecular beam deposition from a resistively heated quartz crucible. The thickness is estimated by quartz micro-balance.

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Figure 1.

Top panels: The quality of Cu(111) surface (a) and the growth of iron film (b) was monitored by STM. CoPc molecules adsorb flat on Fe/Cu(111) surface as shown in STM image (c-d). Bias and tunnelling current of the images: (a) $V_b = -1$ V, $I = 0.08$ nA; (b) $V_b = -0.8$ V, $I = 0.6$ nA; (c) $V_b = -0.6$ V, $I = 0.32$ nA. The scheme of the sample and CoPc molecular structure are reported on top of STM images.

Bottom panels: (e) N 1s XAS spectra measured at $\theta = 60^\circ$ for CoPc(1ML)/Fe/Cu, CoPc(6ML)/Fe/Cu and CoPc(1ML)/Cu. N K XAS spectra recorded for two different orientations of the electric field vector \mathbf{E} parallel and upright to surface by using as angles of incidence 0° and 60° of the synchrotron light according to the experimental geometry shown in the inset for CoPc 1 ML (f) and 6 ML (g). All measurements are performed at room temperature.

Figure 2.

(a) C1s and (b) N1s core-level photoemission spectra of CoPc/Fe(20ML)/Cu(111) at incident photon energy of 480 eV. The bottom spectra of (a) and (b) are C1s and N1s core-level photoemission spectra relative to a monolayer of CoPc grown on Cu(111). (a) Data (dots) and fits (solid line) are shown for monolayer (bottom) and multilayer (top) coverages. The photoemission spectra are aligned with respect to Fermi edge. The intensity of the spectra is normalized to peak height of the most intense component to highlight changes in line shape. Six components of Gaussian profile are used in the curve fitting for C1s spectra (dots) with a FWHM of circa 0.5 eV. They accounts for two different C sites: C_{benz} (thin line) and C_{pyr} (dashed line) within CoPc, their shake-up satellites and vibrational feature (thick line). (c) Co L_3 XAS spectra measured for CoPc films: 1ML (d) and 6ML (c) grown on Fe(20ML)/Cu(111). The spectra are taken at different incident angles θ between the polarization vector E and the normal to the sample surface. All measurements are performed at room temperature.

Figure 3.

Fe L_3 XAS and XMCD spectra of iron film grown on Cu(111). The scheme in panel (a) illustrates the experimental geometry with a magnetic field applied along the sample surface. (b) Element-specific hysteresis loop of ferromagnetic substrate (Fe/Cu(111)) obtained by recording the intensity of Fe L_3 XMCD spectra as a function of applied magnetic field. (c) Co $2p-3d$ XAS spectra measured for CoPc monolayer measured with parallel (thick line) and antiparallel (dots) alignment between photon helicity and magnetic field. All measurements are performed at room temperature.